

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN BACTERIAL COLONIZATION AND INTERLEUKIN-8 SERUM LEVELS IN ACUTE EXACERBATION OF COPD

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ABSTRACT

Background: One of the causes of AECOPD is a bacterial infection. Increased bacterial colonization may trigger activation of macrophages so that there is an increase in the number of inflammatory mediators, one of which is Interleukin-8 (IL-8). Elevation of IL-8 serum levels may worsen the symptoms of COPD. This study measured IL-8 serum levels in subjects who had exacerbations. **Methods:** An analytical research with Cross-Sectional design. The research subjects were AECOPD patients who visited Dr Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital, Makassar, Indonesia. Sputum culture was examined to assess the type of bacterial colonization and serum examined to asses the Interleukin-8 serum levels.

Results: The subjects were 65 patients. AECOPD is generally found in 62 men (95.4%), most were age>60 years 48 patients (73.8%). For severity, we found 52 patients were categorized as group D (80%). The highest number of subjects with bacterial colonization was 55 (84.65). From the subjects with bacterial colonization we found Gram-negative 36 (55.4%). The most types of bacterial were Pseudomonas Aeruginosa with 16 patients (24.65) and Klebsiella Pneumonia in 12 patients (18.5%). Mean IL-8 serum levels 187.5 ± 68.3 . IL-8 serum levels were found highest in subjects who had bacterial colonization 9197.7 ± 68.5 ; $p < 0.05$). Interleukin-8 serum levels increased higher in the Gram-Negative group than Gram-Positive (202.6 vs 188.4, $p > 0.05$).

Discussion: In this research, there was a significant correlation between colonization of Gram-negative bacteria with high IL-8 serum levels. These results are consistent with several studies which report that bacterial colonization is associated with increased IL-8 serum levels and correlates with deterioration in pulmonary function and severity of COPD.

KEYWORDS Chronic Obstructive Exacerbation Pulmonary Disease, Bacterial Colonization, Interleukin-8

Introduction

Acute exacerbation of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease has high morbidity and mortality. One of the trigger factors for the exacerbations is a bacterial infection.[1] Increased number of bacterial will cause inflammation of the airways and accelerate airway obstruction.[2] Increase of inflammatory response during an exacerbation, will lead to increased release of inflammatory mediators. It will aggravate the pathological process associated with decreased pulmonary function.[3] Fujimoto et al. and Bathoorn et al. reported that in AECOPD there was an increase in inflammatory mediators such as Interleukin-8 compared to

stable COPD.[4,5]

An increase in the colonization of both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria may trigger exacerbation conditions. Celli and Barnes reported that AECOPD was mostly caused by an infection of *Haemophilus influenzae* or *Streptococcus pneumoniae*[6]. Moreover, Miravittles et al. also reported a severe association of exacerbations with Gram-negative infections, mainly by *Pseudomonas* spp.[7]

Various studies also reported that an increase in the number of airway bacterial was closely related to several inflammatory markers, one of which was Interleukin-8. Desai et al. reported that IL-8 levels were higher during the period of bacterial colonization.[2] This increase of IL-8 levels may worsen the COPD symptoms.

In our study, we evaluated the correlation between bacterial colonization and IL-8 serum levels. Moreover, we also evaluated the types of bacterial which most caused an increase of IL-8 serum levels in AECOPD patients.

Methods

This research involved 65 AECOPD patients at Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital with a cross-sectional analytic design from August 2018 to January 2019. This research was approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Medicine with reference number: 12/UN4.6.4.5.31/PP36-KOMETIK/2019. The diagnosis of COPD is based on history, physical examination, and results of FEV1/FVC <0.70. Establishment of exacerbations based on Anthonisen criteria. Determination of severity was based on the results of the CAT and mMRC questionnaire, history of exacerbations, and history of hospitalization. All subjects perform anamnesis, physical examination, CAT and mMRC questionnaire, additional laboratory tests, Interleukin-8 serum levels and sputum culture examination to assess the type of bacterial. Interleukin-8 serum levels were examined in the Microbiology laboratory of Unhas Hospital, using the ELISA method. Examination of sputum culture was conducted in the Clinical Pathology Laboratory of Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital. Data analysis using SPSS version 22. The statistical analysis was descriptive statistic calculation and frequency distribution, and also Independent-t statistical test, ANOVA, and Chi-Square test. The results are significant if the value $p < 0.05$.

Results

We found 63 subjects aged between 50-91 years, age mean 66.8 ± 9.6 years. Most subjects were men (95.4%) with ages >60 years (73.8%). Based on BMI, the most nutritional status was normoweight in 40 subjects (61.5%). Smoking status based on Brinkman index was a moderate smoker in 31 subjects (47.7%). Based on the results of spirometry, most subjects were categorized as severe and very severe obstruction (61.5%). Based on the severity of the disease, most subjects were in group D (80%) (Table 1). Based on sputum culture results, most subjects had gram-negative bacteria (55.4%). The highest types of bacterias were *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (24.6%), *Klebsiella Pneumonia* (18.5%), and *Streptococcus Pneumonia* (16.95). (Table 2). Interleukin-8 serum levels were ranged from 81.2-511.1 mean 187.5 ± 68.3 .

The mean of IL-8 serum was significantly higher in the group with colonization than in the group without colonization (197.7 vs 131.2) with ($p < 0.01$). (Table 4). Then, we analyzed the correlation of IL-8 serum levels according to the results of gram-positive

and gram negative cultures with the results showed that IL-8 serum levels were higher in gram-negative (202.6) than in gram-positive (188.4), but statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). (Table 5)

Discussion

Pulmonary function in COPD caused by the damage and the remodelling of the large and small airways. This is caused by chronic inflammation due to the complex interactions between the ambient (toxic inhalation and microbial changes) and the airway mucosa (immune response) which involves infiltration of various inflammatory cells including neutrophils, macrophages, lymphocytes, and mast cells. Changes in inflammation and decreased lung function become more apparent at each exacerbation. Cigarette smoke and another irritant can activate the macrophages in airways, then releasing various factors of neutrophil chemoattractant, one of which is Interleukin-8. These cells later release proteases which trigger fibrosis in the pulmonary parenchyma, results in emphysema and also stimulate mucus hypersecretion.[8]

The mechanism of airway remodelling is still debated. Airway remodelling is marked by changes in tissue, cells, and molecular components, thus contributing to pathological changes in smooth muscle epithelial cells and blood vessels. It is known that the inflammatory process in the airways is mostly caused by smoking and is worsened by the bacterial infections, although this can also occur in ex-smokers. One experimental study showed that direct exposure to cigarette smoke can cause changes in cell structure in lung tissue as a result of inflammatory responses and oxidative stress.[9]

Interleukin-8 is a strong neutrophil chemoattractant incorporated in the CXC family. Interleukin-8 is one of the main mediators of the inflammatory response. Interleukin-8 is made and released by bronchial epithelial cells, monocytes, macrophages, and neutrophils. The main function of IL-8 is activation and neutrophils recruitment to the site of infection or injury to phagocytes antigens. The increased concentrations of IL-8 are found in inflammatory diseases, such as Psoriasis, Rheumatoid Arthritis, respiratory syncytial virus infections, or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. IL-8 levels in patients with COPD can be examined through sputum or serum.[10] Cigarette smoke is a strong source of stimulation for the release of IL-8. One study showed that IL-8 levels increased drastically in the sputum of patients with COPD and related to the severity of the disease.[11] The ability of IL-8 to recruit and activate leukocytes is a key part of initiating an inflammatory response to foreign agents and has been associated with various airway inflammation, including COPD.[10] The calculation of IL-8 levels is one of the best markers for assessing the severity of COPD.[12] This is consistent with a study conducted by Qiu, et al. that there was an increase in the expression of IL-8 in both sputum and serum in patients with AECOPD who experienced extubation. [13]

The increased levels of IL-8 serum in COPD, in particular, the exacerbation phase can be influenced by many things, such as the degree of obstruction, severity, and the number of comorbidities. However, the condition of the infection can further increase the levels of serum IL-8. The condition of COPD exacerbation occurs when the amount of pathogenic bacterial colonization increases or there are new strains of infection that can trigger phagocytosis and activation of macrophages thus releasing Leukotriene B4 (LTB4), Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF a) and IL-8. When colonization of bacterial increases, overexpression

Table 1. Subject Characteristic (n=65)

Variable		n	%
Sex	Male	62	95.4
	Female	3	4.6
Age	<60 years	17	26.2
	>=60 years	48	73.8
BMI	Underweight	15	23.1
	Normoweight	40	61.5
	Overweight	10	15.4
Smoking Status	Mild	15	23.1
	Moderate	31	47.7
	Heavy	19	29.2
GOLD/ Obstruction Levels	Mild	9	13.8
	Moderate	16	24.6
	Severe	27	41.5
Severity Levels	Very Severe	13	20.0
	Group C*	13	20.0
	Group D	52	80.0
Culture Results	Gram Positive	19	29.2
	Gram-Negative	36	55.4
	No Culture	10	15.4

Table 2. Type of Colonization and Type of Bacterial

Type of Colonization	Bacteria	N	%
Gram Negative (55.4%)	Pseudomonas Aeroginosa	16	24.6
3*	Klebsiella Pneumonia	12	18.5
	Enterobacter Cloacae	5	7.7
	Acinetobacter Baumannii	3	4.6
Gram Negative (29.2%)	Streptococcus Pneumonia	11	16.9
	Streptococcus parasanguinis	8	12.3
Other	Candida, et al	10	15.4

Table 3. IL-8 serum levels (n=65)

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	SD
IL-8 level	81.2	511.1	187.5	68.3

Table 4. IL-8 serum levels according to Colonization of Bacterial

Bacterial Colonization	n	Mean	SD	P
2* Yes	55	197.7	68.5	0.004
No	10	131.2	29.4	

Table 5. IL-8 serum levels according to Culture

Culture Results	n	Mean	SD	P
2* Gram Positive	19	188.4	28.4	0.352
Gram Negative	36	202.6	82.2	

occurs of adhesion molecules results in increased adhesion and aggregation on the number of neutrophils, which will increase the expression of neutrophil elastase, where all of this will trigger exacerbations.[14] Our study shows a significant correlation between bacterial colonization with high serum IL-8 levels. It is stated that serum IL-8 is related to the bacterial colonization, which shows that bacterial colonization plays a role in the inflammatory process of the lower airway and causes an increase in the degree of pulmonary obstruction. Hill et al. reported that an increase in the number of airway bacterial was closely related to several inflammatory markers in sputum, including IL-8 levels.[15] Desai et al. reported that IL-8 levels were higher during the period of bacterial colonization and concluded that increased IL-8 levels could worsen the COPD symptoms.[2]

Our study found the average results of the highest levels of serum IL-8 in Gram-Negative cultures as many as 202.6 with the most types of *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (24.6%). These results show a significant correlation between bacterial colonization, particularly Gram-negative with high levels of serum IL-8.[15] The research results are consistent with the report of Narayanagowda et al. who obtained more Gram-negative bacteria in AECOPD. It is mentioned that Gram-Negative bacteria is more common in patients who have more severe lung function damage.[16] Lin et al. also reported an increase in Gram-negative infections, including *Klebsiella pneumonia* (19.6%) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (16.8%) in hospitalized patients with AECOPD.[14]

Furthermore, Kuwal, et al. also reported that of 34 patients with AECOPD, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (38.23%) was the most dominant organism followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (29.41%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (23.53%), and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (5.88%).[17] *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection is more common in patients with worse lung function.[18] From this study, we concluded that the higher bacterial colonization, the higher the Interleukin-8 serum levels.

Competing Interests

No conflict of Interest.

Ethics committee approval

This research was approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Medicine with reference number: 12/UN4.6.4.5.31/PP36-KOMETIK/2019.

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